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Editor´s note

We are pleased to share with you the first issue of the Punto Crítico (Critical Point) newsletter by the MeCCS team. A critical point occurs when a substance has an identical form in the liquid and gas phases under specific conditions of temperature and pressure. At the critical point, therefore, the boundaries between liquid and gas phases are eliminated. With this publication we seek to situate ourselves at a critical point where boundaries between highly technical and specialized knowledge on issues of carbon capture and sustainability are dissolved to make them accessible to all the public interested in them.

In this issue you will find two news stories that explain how Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies work, and a couple of infographics related to the topics in the “Sí, sí es” (Yes, yes it is) section. Additionally, in the “CO₂NVERSANDO” (CO₂NVERSING) section, you will find an interview with Dr Omar Masera Cerutti, a researcher at the UNAM Ecosystem and Sustainability Research Institute, in which we address the role of technology as an intermediary and fundamental bridge between the human-environment relationship and in the creation of sociotechnoecological systems. Finally, the “Para llevar” (Take-away) section contains recommendations for books, videos, podcasts and additional materials that will allow you to delve into the topics covered in this newsletter. We hope you enjoy this issue and, if you wish, contact our team to send us your comments or topics of interest.

STAR WARS, BIOMIMICRY AND CARBON CAPTURE

Adrián Fernández

John Williams created the music for Star Wars based on the work of Erich Wolfgang Korngold, an Austrian composer from the first half of the 20th century who, due to his genius, was nicknamed "the new Mozart". Korngold was one of the forerunners of film music and for John Williams he has always represented an artistic ideal. This implies, in the words of Williams himself, that "some works are very similar from a thematic point of view, but in terms of melody and harmony, all the notes are mine". As proof of this, it is enough to listen to the theme of the 1942 movie *Kings Row* and compare it with the main theme of *Star Wars* (I hope you are currently going on YouTube or Spotify to hear that similarity). Williams has stated on several occasions that he would never have been able to write the music for *Star Wars* without Korngold's influence; in the same way that there would not have been a Wagner, as we know him, without a previous Beethoven. Williams, without losing his essence, "blended himself" into Korngold's music.

The word mimesis comes from the Greek μίμησις, which means imitation. Without a doubt, we adopt some appearance or behavior more often than we realize. For example, when two people like each other have a coffee, they often unconsciously reflect non-verbal language. Even after observing some couples who have been married for many years, we have concluded that both bear a resemblance to each other. In 1987, Robert Zajonc, a pioneer in social psychology, designed a study in which participants were given a random arrangement of face pictures (with a black background to avoid bias from the context) and asked to match men and women which, in his opinion, "were more alike". In these images, there were newly married couples and photos of the same marriages 25 years later. In the eyes of participants in the study, young couples did not show many similarities, but there were some very clear subtle traits in couples who were about to celebrate their silver wedding anniversary. In fact, participants were able to find more easily which pair of photos corresponded to married couples after 25 years of marriage. Mirror neurons, which act in a similar way both when performing an action and simply observing it, are involved in our ability to learn by imitation. This is most clearly reflected in the face, given the number of muscles that relax and contract in order to adopt the appearance of a conversational partner.

Studies on mimesis are not new, especially in biology. In the mid-19th century, Englishman Henry Bates abandoned his position as a storekeeper and embarked on an 11-year near-suicide mission to the Brazilian Amazon to study insects, his passion as an amateur entomologist. He studied animal mimicry and published the first work on the subject: he observed that some butterflies of the genus *Leptalis* mimicked some species of the genus *Ithomia* to avoid being eaten by their predators. Bates concluded that, although *Ithomia* butterflies are more abundant and slower than *Leptalis*, their smell and taste are not pleasant, hence predators avoid them and prefer the faster - and tastier - *Leptalis*.

Biomimicry is precisely the emulation or imitation of natural models or systems in order to solve a socio-environmental problem. It is about innovation inspired by nature: make a solar cell based on the shape and functions of a leaf; create strong and flexible support structures based on spider webs; design an agricultural system based on patterns and relationships that would exist in an ecosystem (permaculture, for example); or base the conception and design of an airplane on the flight of vultures, as the Wright brothers did at the beginning of the 20th century.

BIOMIMICRY AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH CARBON SEQUESTRATION

One of the greatest current challenges is to counteract the anthropogenic emission of greenhouse gasses, mainly carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides and water vapor, released as a product of the combustion of hydrocarbons for energy production, which have become the main responsible for global warming. One of the technological approaches that has been developed to deal with this problem is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS).

Broadly speaking, and with the risk of falling into an oversimplification, carbon capture and storage technologies involve the capture of gasses at the site where they are emitted by an industry (thermoelectric, for example), their subsequent concentration, compression and transportation are necessary steps to finally be injected into deep geological formations. The development of a range of techniques to capture greenhouse gas emissions is critical to keeping global warming at bay. The technique described above has a physicochemical approach, but a biomimetic vision has also begun to emerge in the field of carbon capture and storage.

A crucial step in the carbon capture process is the mineralization of carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a carbonate, because carbonates constitute a potential CO₂ sink that is ubiquitous and geologically and ecologically secure. To facilitate this conversion, biological accelerators of chemical reactions, such as enzymes, can be used. Such is the case of bovine carbonic anhydrases, which have proven to be suitable for the transformation of carbon dioxide into carbonates. This method could avoid a costly step in conventional CCS techniques, which involves regulating some specific conditions of temperature, pressure and pH. Of course, the great challenge of transferring this process to an industrial scale still remains, since it has only been tested in laboratories.

Another complementary proposal for the CO₂ injection stage in geological formations is the use of calcifying microorganisms to carry out biocementation. This process involves injecting calcifying organisms – bacteria, fungi, and algae can be a winning combo – into underground formations along with captured CO₂, as well as additional oxygen and nutrients needed for the organisms to survive. With this strategy, it is sought that, just as a coral would do, these species promote formation and precipitation of carbonates in the geological layer where they were inoculated. This would prevent possible CO₂ leaks through some interstices and would work as an additional step to its stabilization and sequestration.

Aristotle said that art imitates nature. The poet John Keats, for his part, wrote that the poetry of the earth never dies. Perhaps it is time to direct the technique and science to the imitation of natural processes as a model and standard of measurement. As an example of this, it is enough to mention that our best solar cell has an average theoretical efficiency of just over 30% (although Geisz and his collaborators published in 2020 that they achieved a 47% conversion of light energy into electricity), while an average purple bacterium uses solar energy with more than 90% efficiency for its life processes.

After 4.5 billion years of existence, nature –biotic and abiotic– leaves us a legacy of what works, what is appropriate, what lasts and what is sustained in space and time. Nature is one of the best teachers one can have and is always teaching, day and night, for whoever is willing to observe, feel and listen. We need to connect with the mimetic faculty that brings us closer to being part of nature, instead of being apart. Nature knows best, some say.

Choreographies for carbon capture, dancing to the same rhythm

Jazmín Mota y Jessica Arellano

W

hen a dance routine is created, including different elements that are grouped and ordered through sequences and patterns, we call it a choreography. As in mathematics, a sequence is a numbered collection in which repetitions are allowed and the order in which they occur matters. In our attempt to understand the world around us, we have discovered that the choreographic process also occurs in nature as a means of communication between cells, molecules and atoms. We can observe it in the cell membrane of a neuron or in the DNA molecules of our chromosomes, in ocean and atmospheric currents, and even in the movement of planets and stars. Wherever we look, a dance occurs where each element of the choreography performs its part exactly in the place and at the time it is their turn to do so

Just as in a choreography, when we analyze complex systems, we find a set of connected elements that feedback and organize themselves in a non-linear way. Thanks to the study of these systems, we can analyze biological processes, climatic or social phenomena. The carbon cycle is an example of the connection between the atmosphere, hydrosphere, biosphere and geosphere, through which CO₂ travels and is transformed at variable rates and scales that influence the ecological and social dynamics of the planet.

The Earth's atmosphere is composed predominantly of nitrogen (78%) and oxygen (21%), while carbon dioxide, argon, water vapor and other gasses together account for the remaining 1%. CO₂ is a greenhouse gas that exists naturally in the atmosphere and whose concentrations are naturally in balance through photosynthesis and through its absorption in soils and oceans. The geological record –in rocks and ice cores– provides us with information about variations in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations that have triggered major transformations over millions of years. In the last 250 years, human activities have rapidly released large amounts of CO₂ into the atmosphere due to the intensive use of fossil fuels, leading us towards another great global change that marks the leap into a new geological age.

Given that the natural processes to balance current CO₂ emissions in the atmosphere are not enough, humans - the main cause of the current imbalance - have explored technologies to make use of CO₂, developed other forms of energy generation and consumption, and reduced the environmental and social impact of industrial activities.

Microsoft, for example, has decided to invest in projects to reduce emissions, among which is direct air capture (DAC) where the CO₂ "sucked" from the atmosphere is transformed into minerals by injecting it into geothermal fields. Another case is Elon Musk's XPrize initiative, which seeks technologies to transform CO₂ into fuel for its space projects. Companies and governments are convinced that technology can help solve the problem of emissions, but there are still several challenges to make these work at the right scale. As presented in the book "The Ministry for the Future" by Kim Stanley Robinson, technology alone will not be able to solve global problems stemming from systemic and structural flaws in the political and social

environment. In his novel, Robinson points out the importance of political innovation, organization of society and use of technology in search for solutions to the problems of the future –which, by the way, we are already experiencing and are not fiction–.

When we are faced with the need to implement new technologies, we must analyze and understand them as systems in all their complexity. There is much more than just a bunch of devices, machinery and software. The system also includes human and institutional interactions that in practice, as in a choreography, should not be seen as a dictatorship where one person or institution tells others what to do, but rather as a collaborative process which requires a bit of trial and error before arriving at the final result. One of the technologies that offers an alternative for the control of anthropogenic GHG emissions is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), where one of the greatest challenges is directly linked to the creation of a collaborative model for its implementation. ▶

Industry, hand in hand with academia, is in charge of exploring solutions to control anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, but there is also an active role on the part of society as consumers, and of governments when setting the objectives, rules and strategies that guide us towards

a fairer and more sustainable future. We need all the elements of the choreography to perform their part in the right place and time.

For this we can learn from how other beings on the planet organize themselves and act to create systems that work efficiently. Termites or ants, for example, self-organize to build and defend their nests, collect and manage their food, and manage their waste without the need for a leader. Fascinating, isn't it?

Although technologies such as CCS offer an alternative for reduction of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, we cannot expect them to solve the entire problem. In any case, it would be worth asking ourselves if what we are waiting to act depends on a hierarchical model where a person decides what, how and when we should act, or if we can create self-organized systems. When it comes to collaboration, it is important to focus on individual work without forgetting that we are part of a collective effort. As a dance teacher says: "In a choreography no one is essential, but we are all important".

Carbon capture and storage

▶ Carbon capture and storage is a technological proposal for the control of CO₂ emissions derived from human activities. It consists of four main stages that include (1) the capture of CO₂ in emission sources of industrial origin that are later (2) transported to places where it can be (3) permanently stored in geological formations. The entire process requires, along its lifetime, (4) a monitoring plan. We can add a fifth stage if we talk about the (5) use of CO₂, which can encompass the manufacture of materials such as plastics or minerals, the growth of plants in greenhouses, its use as fuel or in oil production processes (enhanced recovery of oil or EOR).

Emission sources can be industrial plants such as cement plants, refineries, petrochemical or gas processing plants, as well as power generation plants. The emissions are produced mainly from burning fossil fuels or as part of industrial processes. The capture can occur before or after the burning of the fuels through different methods that can be physical, chemical or a combination of both.

For its transport, the CO₂ is compressed until it reaches the liquid state. The most common method of transporting CO₂ is by pipeline, but there are other options such as trucks and tankers. The selection of the type of transport depends on the gas amount and distance from source to sink, since the emission sources are not –necessarily– located at the storage site.

For its storage, the CO₂ is injected into large rock bodies that are more than 800 meters deep. These rocks can have water, oil or gas in their micropores with which the CO₂ is mixed and retained. The geological options suitable for CO₂ storage are oil or gas reservoirs and deep saline aquifers (the latter are totally different from the groundwater or fresh water reservoirs). Another type of storage is mineral carbonation where chemical processes predominate to form minerals; however, this method is less common.

The monitoring process is crucial to ensure that the state of the transport infrastructure is in optimal conditions in order to avoid leaks. During the injection, it is crucial to avoid over-pressure the rocks to avoid fractures and contain the CO₂, so that it does not migrate vertically towards the surface. Likewise, some geophysical and geochemical techniques help to monitor the properties of water and soil in more superficial layers to detect any leaks.

Each of the activities is carried out by a different sector and industry that requires establishing a sequence of actions, rules and standards aligned with the common objective of reducing and controlling CO₂ emissions. The active and permanent participation of industry, academia, society and government are essential from the earliest planning stage to the projects closing and monitoring.

CONVERSANDO

CONVERSING

Technology as a link between the human being and the environment

Interview with **Omar Masera Cerutti**

Ecosystem and Sustainability Research Institute, UNAM

Mariana Velázquez Cárdenas

Omar Masera Cerruti a physicist from the Faculty of Sciences at UNAM and has a master's degree and a PhD in Energy and Natural Resource Management from the University of Berkeley, where he studied, among other things, the interactions between technology, environment and society. He is currently a researcher at the Ecosystem and Sustainability Research Institute, UNAM, where he directs the Ecotechnological and Bioenergy Innovation Group. His work involves the study of bioenergy issues, rural ecotechnologies, climate change mitigation, and sustainability analysis from a systemic, interdisciplinary and different scales perspectives.

In his research on rural energy, he has focused on the analysis of bioenergy through the concept of transformative and participatory innovation, which involves the development of technological alternatives for and with the people. In particular, he has developed technology in the field of rural domestic cooking, such as the Patsari stove, which has international recognition. Since 1998 he has participated as an international expert from Mexico before the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), an organization that received the Nobel Peace Prize in 2007.

This first CO₂NVERSANDO interview addresses technology as a mediator between the society-environment relationship. We discussed the importance of transdisciplinary research for the study of sociotechnoecological systems and the impact of adopting this approach in the evaluation and selection of technologies. To delve into these issues, we interviewed Dr. Omar Masera Cerutti:

M- In 2019 you published, together with some Mexican and Swedish colleagues, the article "Bringing Technology into Social-Ecological Systems Research—Motivations for a Socio-Technical-Ecological Systems Approach"; in it, they explain their motivations for adopting an approach where technology went from being an exogenous factor to a more relevant element in the study of socio-ecological systems. **Can you tell us how the idea of uniting socio-ecological systems with socio-technical ones was born? And how did this new proposal come about?**

O - At the Ecosystem and Sustainability Research Institute where I work, considerable emphasis is placed on **systemic thinking** and that forces us to understand the interrelationships that some things have with others. In particular, a very important aspect within the study of technology has been to understand how its

relationships and interrelationships with society and the environment occur.

The study of the relationship between technology and society, or what we can call **socio-technical systems**, has a long tradition and allows us to understand how the design and diffusion of technological innovations depend not only on engineering variables (such as cost, efficiency, etc.), but also of the social, cultural and political environment in which they are developed (See, as a reference, Basalla's book [2] in the section "To take away"). On the other hand, the relationship between technology and environment has been studied for many years, in what would be the field of **environmental engineering**. There is also literature that for many years has been talking about **socio-ecological systems**, where the relationship between society and environment is prioritized. However, each of these fields rarely "talk to each other" which is very worrying in the current context in which social, environmental and technological problems are so intertwined.

It was missing a way to integrate the three social, technological and environmental perspectives in a new conceptual framework, which in the article we call "socio-techno-ecological systems" (STES) where we can consider technology as a link between the human being and the environment.

Indeed, practically any interaction between human beings or between society and the environment is mediated by technology. Technology does not have a passive relationship or an independent dynamic of society and the environment, but a dialectical relationship, in other words, it is conditioned by the socio-environmental context in which it develops and can create new conditions or "surprises". " not foreseen in its origin (think of the case of the internet or electricity). These considerations force us to speak of **sociotechnoecological or sociotechnoenvironmental systems** and analyze problems as complex as climate change, the energy transition process and others from this perspective.

M -Precisely, we see this relationship between technology, society and environment throughout the development of our activities as human beings; however, when it comes to research, we hardly see the papers being inclusive. **What do you think is the reason for this and what is needed to address an approach that integrates both systems?**

O - Science, especially since the 20th century, has opted for reductionism as the central focus of research. This meant dividing reality into a greater number of disciplines that examine more and more particular aspects of the problems and that rarely communicate with each other. That thinking led us to great discoveries, but it has also been increasingly inadequate to understand problems where social, economic, cultural, technological and basic science aspects are intimately related, such as the problem of climate change.

In fact, we can say that since the end of the 20th century and in the 21st century, the importance of the **interdisciplinary and systemic perspective** has been increasingly recognized. Perhaps one of the most interesting examples of this type of perspective are the IPCC reports, in which a very broad group of scientists meet in interdisciplinary working groups to seek solutions to the problem of climate change, including ethical, economic, social, ecological, technological and biophysical perspectives.

To further promote this type of approach we need , on the one hand, to include social science courses in more technical careers and vice versa, environmental and technical issues in social science careers, since it is critical to develop integrative approaches from training students. We must also set up truly interdisciplinary work teams, promote group theses and final year projects. It is currently impossible to develop technological alternatives -as is the case of carbon capture and storage technologies, which this magazine is focused on - without fully understanding their environmental implications, or without critically asking: who benefits? How are they going to really contribute to a fairer and more sustainable society?

M - In your opinion, **how do you consider that the study of sociotechnoecological systems can contribute to the evaluation and selection of technologies?**

O - Sociotechnoecological systems force us to examine technology in its interrelationships with society and the environment. Likewise, from this perspective, end users -and other social actors involved in the use of the technology in question, or who may be impacted by it- are understood as part of the system and as an integral element of any project of change, technology innovation or design.

This perspective contrasts with the conventional view, where technology evaluation is done from a purely economic perspective -based on one or two parameters such as the internal rate of return, etc.- or, at most, including environmental impact studies. But the problem is that they end up being something like "I choose the alternatives and then I tell people which one to agree with and which one I don't agree with", that is, consulting people at the end of the process. Now, a great movement within the field of **technological innovation** speaks of the need for **participatory processes**, where people collaborate and give their opinions, from the design of alternatives to their implementation and monitoring. The important thing about this perspective is that it puts on the table many more options than those originally considered by the "experts", opening the possibility of a true and successful dialogue of knowledge between the various social actors involved in the process. For example, if, as is happening now with mining projects or mega renewable energy projects, developers need access to the territory of native communities, they would have to work with them from the beginning to see if the proposed alternatives really interest them. Or if rather we have to fundamentally rethink this extractivist logic and develop other more sustainable and democratic alternatives.

As engineers and scientists, this new approach causes us many problems because we have been taught from the beginning of our studies that experts are the only ones who can give their opinion and that local knowledge is not valid or is simply linked to ignorance. Therefore, we think that the only ones who can say something are us, but this has been increasingly questioned, especially when the alternatives, as the case of technologies that are being discussed to reduce climate change, will have a significant impact in the standard of living of people, in the quality of the environment and in the access to resources of the same communities. For these reasons, it is very important to "turn around" these vertical schemes and learn to walk together with different social actors in order to develop true social and environmentally sustainable alternatives.

Reference

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2. Basalla, George, 2011, La evolución de la tecnología, Ed. Crítica. (Barcelona)

SÍ, SÍ ES

YES, YES IT IS

In the following infographics you will find information on 1) the volume that CO₂ emissions would occupy if we could observe them with the naked eye and some reference objects whose size we know to compare, and 2) the places where CO₂ is stored naturally. Both graphs will be useful to put into perspective the problem of greenhouse gas emissions and their storage.

CO₂ is a colorless gas that we cannot see, but whose high concentration in the atmosphere and in the oceans has great repercussions on ecological and social systems.

We refer to CO₂ emissions in tons, millions of tons or billions of tons, but have you ever wondered what those amounts are or what their size would be if we could see them?

Values under standard conditions
 Temperature = 0°C
 Pressure = 101 325 Pascals

1 ton = 1000 kilograms

What would the size of the emissions look like?

1 ton (t) = 8 m cube per side

100 tons = 38 m cube per side

115 m Hyperion (Secuoya)

The Hyperion is the tallest tree on the planet (115 m) and is located in northern California, USA.

The Angel of Independence is an emblematic monument of Mexico City (45 m).

45 m
The Angel of the Independence

100 megatons (Mt) = 820 m cube per side

The Torre Latinoamericana (182 m) was the tallest skyscraper in Latin America until 1984.

We would have to stack 4.5 towers to get the approximate height of a 820 m cube.

1 gigaton (Gt) = 8 km cube per side

The Pico de Orizaba (5.6 km) It is the highest mountain in Mexico.

The Mount Everest (8.8 km) is the highest mountain on the planet.

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- <https://alcaldiacuauhtemoc.mx/nope/angel-de-la-independencia/>
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- <https://www.geoenciclopedia.com/pico-de-orizaba/>

Natural CO₂ sinks

Millions of years ago, the plants, algae and plankton that inhabited the Earth captured large amounts of CO₂. When these organisms died, and due to geological processes, they were transformed into deposits of coal, oil and gas that we extract today.

Although the biosphere and soils seem vast, their contribution to the carbon cycle is small compared to other systems.

Huge amounts of CO₂ are stored in the lithosphere as rocks (crust) and magma (mantle).

CO₂ in the lithosphere can be released into the atmosphere by volcanic or industrial processes (eg cement production).

The largest contribution to the natural storage of CO₂ occurs in the oceans through dissolved inorganic carbon that forms large deposits of marine carbonate rocks and is used by some marine animals to form their shells. According to National Oceanic, cooler regions (the North Atlantic and the Arctic) are capable of absorbing more CO₂ than warmer areas. This occurs because the solubility of a gas in water increases as the temperature decreases, and vice versa.

References:

Carbon cycling & sequestration (SERC, 2021)
Carbon sinks and sequestration (UNECE, 2021)
The ocean carbon cycle (IAEEA, 2021)
The carbon cycle (NASA, 2011)

Why does cold water take in more CO₂ than warmer water and hold it better? (Quora, 2021)

PARA LLEVAR TAKE-AWAY

In the material we recommend for this issue, you can find information on conferences, courses, books, films and podcasts related to sustainability. In addition, you will find different materials that address contributions of technology to sustainable development, as well as its scope and limitations.

The Mexican Petroleum Congress 2022

The CMP 2022 will take place from July 6 to 9 in Villahermosa, Tabasco, Mexico. In accordance with the call opening, this year the area of Environmental, Health and Safety emphasizes the relevance of Sustainability and Sustainable Development. The deadline for submitting proposals is April 30, 2022.

Check the call for papers in the following link:
https://congresomexicanodelpetroleo.com/Convocatoria_trabajos.html

CLIMITOLOGY Podcast

Episode 4 of the Climatology podcast, produced by the UNAM Climate Change Research Program, seeks to debunk the myth that new technologies are our last hope to tackle climate change. The podcast contains an interview with Jazmín Mota, a geological engineer from UNAM, and Omar Masera, a physicist at the UNAM Ecosystem and Sustainability Research Institute.

Listen to the podcast in the following link:
<https://www.pincc.unam.mx/climitologia/episodio-4/>

Book: *Homo Deus - A Brief History of Tomorrow*

In this book, Yuval Noah Harari explores how the future of humanity could be defined by technological disruptions, which could change global power and governance dynamics as well as evolutionary processes. The book presents a summary of how technology can be decisive for the dreams and nightmares that will shape the 22nd century.

Book: *Big World, Small Planet: Abundance within planetary boundaries*

Johan Rockström, a Swedish scientist recognized for his work on global sustainability issues, and Matthias Klum, a photographer who works for National Geographic, join their talents to write a work that aims to emphasize the need for a change in the mindset of development, whose goal is to achieve abundance within the limits and borders that our own planet imposes on us.

Documentary: *David Attenborough: A Life on Our Planet*

This documentary represents the testimony of the life of David Attenborough, a British naturalist and communicator who has spent many years documenting the living world on all continents. In this autobiographical work, Attenborough reflects on the future of humanity and the urgent need to follow more sustainable paths.

<https://www.ourplanet.com/es/video/david-attenborough-a-life-on-our-planet-trailer/>

Summer Course in Iceland

Energy is a Mexican startup focused on education that has designed a summer course called Iceland 2022: a sustainable experience. Through 3 axes that include talks with experts and decision makers, technical visits to renewable energy and carbon capture plants, and guided visits to natural areas and cultural places, Energy offers an immersive experience on sustainability. Dates: June 27 to July 8, 2022.

Check the information in the following link:
<https://www.energyou.org/curso-de-verano-islandia>

Book: *The evolution of technology*

This book, written in 1989 by George Basalla, exposes the author's ideas about the "evolutionary" and "revolutionary" positions previously raised by other authors as a way of analyzing technological development. His "theory of technological evolution" places special emphasis on the role of the social, political and economic context in technological change using three main concepts: continuity, novelty and selection. From these principles, Basalla demonstrates that all artifacts, real or made, that we have built have their antecedents in the natural world.

Exhibition: *No sound of water*

This exhibition is presented in the Plaza Artz Pedregal, Mexico City, Mexico, in a space called Open Art. The exhibition is about how to see, know and reflect on nature and technology, virtual and real, and about the human and non-human. This exhibition seeks to reflect on the future of the Earth and its transformation into an inhospitable place due to human activity. You can visit this exhibition until May 15, 2022.

<http://arteabierto.org/troika-micrositio/>

Chapter series: *Abstract: bioarchitecture*

Learn about the work of Professor Neri Oxman's team from the MIT Media Lab in the Netflix series Abstract (episode 2, season 2). Neri Oxman's vision is to design materials that emulate nature to counteract the ecological crisis. Her projects integrate interdisciplinary teams and combine science, art, engineering and design to create proposals with a holistic approach.

<https://www.netflix.com/search?q=abstract&jbv=80057883>

Book: *Ethics and technological world*

In this book, Jorge Enrique Linares presents a philosophical reflection about Heidegger, Anders, Ellul, Jonas and Nicol ideas. Linares exposes alternatives to build an ethical vision of the technological world that allows reconciling the relationship between technology, society and ecosystems. In this way, he seeks to provide a solution to the ethical vacuum that he identifies, through a series of principles related to responsibility, justice, precaution and autonomy.

Mexico City, Mexico, 2022